

THE IMPACT OF OBESITY ON THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM

Nurulloev Jo'rabek Shavkiddinovich

Assistant reacher of the Alfraganus university

ORCID ID: 0009-0003-4777-1881

Email: JurabekDoctor@mail.ru

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Abstract

The prevalence of obesity is escalating globally, posing a significant health challenge. Its impact on cardiovascular health stems from both the direct effects of obesity and its association with various comorbidities such as hypertension, diabetes, insulin resistance, and sleep apnea syndrome. Atherosclerosis and coronary artery disease are notably exacerbated by obesity. Structural and functional alterations of the heart induced by obesity contribute to the development of heart failure, while the modified myocardial structure heightens susceptibility to atrial fibrillation and sudden cardiac death. Intriguingly, obesity exhibits a paradoxical protective effect on the clinical outcomes of underlying cardiovascular diseases, termed the "obesity paradox." Advancements in cardiac imaging techniques enable the early identification of cardiac structural and functional changes in obese individuals. This review aims to elucidate the intricate relationship between obesity and cardiovascular diseases, delineating the underlying mechanisms. Moreover, it highlights emerging cardiac diagnostic methods that facilitate the timely detection and management of subclinical conditions, thereby averting cardiovascular events.

Keywords: Obesity, atherosclerosis, endothelial dysfunction, cholesterol, hypercoagulability, vascular lesions.

The Connection between Obesity and Atherosclerosis

Over the past three decades, significant insights into the pathophysiological mechanisms linking obesity and atherosclerosis have emerged. Previously viewed primarily as disorders involving lipid accumulation—triglycerides in adipose tissue and cholesterol esters in atherosclerotic plaques—both conditions are now recognized as chronic inflammatory states. In this paradigm shift, the activation of nonspecific and adaptive immune pathways plays a pivotal role.

Common pathways underlie the pathogenesis of obesity and atherosclerosis. Lipids, oxidized LDL particles, and free fatty acids serve as instigators, sparking inflammatory cascades that drive disease progression. Inflammation is central to the entire spectrum of atherosclerotic development, from initial endothelial dysfunction to the formation of complicated plaques, and is intricately linked with obesity, insulin resistance, and type 2 diabetes. Adipose tissue releases adipocytokines that promote insulin resistance, endothelial dysfunction, hypercoagulability, and systemic inflammation, thus facilitating atherosclerosis. In cases of visceral obesity, inflammatory adipocytokines such as TNF- α , IL-6, MCP-1, leptin, and resistin are elevated. Additionally, elevated levels of C-reactive protein are associated with heightened risks of myocardial infarction, peripheral vascular disease, and diabetes mellitus.

Significantly, clinical studies have demonstrated that lifestyle-induced weight loss in obese individuals, particularly women, leads to reductions in inflammatory biomarkers and insulin resistance. Concurrently, there is an increase in adiponectin, an anti-inflammatory

adipocytokine with insulin-sensitizing properties. Understanding the intricate interplay between inflammation and atherosclerosis, particularly the exacerbating influence of obesity, is crucial for effective management and intervention strategies.

Obesity exhibits a close correlation with coronary atherosclerosis.

Findings from studies conducted on young patients indicate that atherosclerosis commences several decades prior to the onset of clinically apparent coronary artery disease. Moreover, individuals with higher BMI values tend to present with more frequent and advanced atherosclerotic vascular lesions compared to those with normal body weight.

Longitudinal studies further emphasize the independent risk posed by obesity in the development of coronary artery disease over at least two decades. Specifically, a 10 kg increase in body weight is associated with a 12% rise in the risk of coronary artery disease, accompanied by concurrent elevations in systolic and diastolic blood pressure by 3 mmHg and 2.3 mmHg, respectively.

Furthermore, in young individuals, excess weight emerges as a primary risk factor for non-ST segment elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI), outweighing the influence of smoking. The onset of NSTEMI tends to occur earlier with increasing BMI. Similar associations are observed in cases of ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), with obesity serving as an independent risk factor for STEMI at a young age.

Moreover, beyond myocardial infarction, obesity is implicated in other vascular events. Each unit increase in BMI is associated with a 4% rise in the risk of ischemic strokes and a 6% increase in the risk of hemorrhagic strokes. These findings underscore the multifaceted impact of obesity on cardiovascular health and the urgency of targeted interventions to mitigate associated risks.

Obesity and Heart Failure

The prevalence of heart failure is on the rise, emerging as a significant global cause of mortality, with approximately 3% prevalence in developed nations. A pronounced association exists between heart failure and obesity. Data from the Framingham Heart Study reveal that each 1 kg/m² increase in BMI escalates the risk of heart failure by 5% in men and 7% in women. Among heart failure patients, 32%–49% are obese and 31%–40% are overweight. Notably, heart failure tends to manifest a decade earlier in obese and overweight individuals compared to those with normal BMI. The duration of morbid obesity closely correlates with the onset of heart failure, with a 70% prevalence increase after 20 years and a 90% increase after 30 years. Structural and functional alterations in the heart observed in obesity contribute significantly to myocardial dysfunction, often termed "obesity cardiomyopathy." Obesity precipitates heart failure through multiple direct and indirect mechanisms. Hemodynamic changes ensue, marked by elevations in both cardiac output and blood pressure; a 5 kg/m² increase in BMI correlates with a 5 mmHg rise in systolic blood pressure. This phenomenon is associated with heightened activity of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system and sympathetic nervous system. Increased aldosterone levels and mineralocorticoid receptor expression promote interstitial cardiac fibrosis, platelet aggregation, and endothelial dysfunction.

Moreover, inflammatory cytokines elevated in obesity—such as TNF- α , IL-1, IL-6, and IL-8—significantly contribute to heart failure development. These mediators induce myocardial fibrosis, increasing myocardial stiffness and potentially leading to diastolic and later systolic heart failure. Leptin and adiponectin, through their metabolic and structural effects, directly

influence myocardial transformation. Additionally, triglyceride accumulation in cardiac muscle, common in obese patients, fosters the generation of toxic metabolites, exacerbating cardiomyocyte apoptosis.

Furthermore, obesity exacerbates heart failure risk not only independently but also through associated medical comorbidities. Insulin resistance, prevalent in obesity, diminishes myocardial contractility and augments the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system activity, potentially leading to myocardial hypertrophy, apoptosis, and fibrosis. Dysregulation of lipid metabolism in obesity heightens atherosclerosis risk, thus contributing to ischemic cardiomyopathy. Myocardial lipid accumulation and fibrosis may also underlie various cardiac arrhythmias, further complicating the course of heart failure.

Obesity and Atrial Fibrillation

Atrial fibrillation stands out among cardiac arrhythmias due to its significant clinical impact. Its prevalence is steadily rising worldwide, affecting approximately 1–2% of the adult population. Atrial fibrillation accounts for approximately one-third of all arrhythmia-related hospitalizations, contributing significantly to morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs. Currently, over 6 million Europeans are afflicted by this arrhythmia, with projections suggesting a doubling of this figure within the next five decades. The incidence of atrial fibrillation exhibits a clear association with age, with prevalence rates increasing from under 0.5% in individuals aged 40–50 to 5–10% in those aged 80 and above. Numerous studies have established a compelling link between obesity and atrial fibrillation. Obese individuals face a 1.52-fold higher risk of developing atrial fibrillation compared to their normal-weight counterparts. Moreover, every one-unit increase in BMI correlates with a 4% rise in the likelihood of newly diagnosed atrial fibrillation.

Furthermore, individuals with atrial fibrillation are at increased risk of adverse outcomes, including sudden cardiac death, stroke, thromboembolic events, and heart failure. Additionally, atrial fibrillation prolongs hospital stays and exacerbates reductions in quality of life and physical functioning.

Structural and Electrical Remodeling Induced by Obesity

Obesity precipitates a multitude of anatomical and functional alterations that significantly contribute to arrhythmogenesis. Among these changes, left atrial dilation and dysfunction are prominent consequences of obesity. Studies have demonstrated that even a modest 5 mm increase in left atrial cross diameter elevates the likelihood of paroxysmal atrial fibrillation by 1.39 times. Additionally, recent research has corroborated the association between augmented epicardial fat tissue and atrial fibrillation. Through its paracrine influence, epicardial fat fosters the development of atrial interstitial fibrosis. The accumulation of epicardial fat, infiltration of adipocytes into the myocardium, and subsequent fibrosis collectively give rise to heterogeneous atrial pulse conduction, known as anisotropy, which contributes to endo- and epicardial electrical dissociation.

These processes collectively promote the development of atrial reentry, forming the electrophysiological substrate for atrial fibrillation. Investigations in both animal models and humans have revealed that expansion of adipose tissue correlates strongly with inadequate capillarization, leading to myocardial hypoxia. Increased adipocyte necrosis triggers infiltration by macrophages, neutrophils, and lymphocytes, along with the accumulation of

proinflammatory cytokines. Moreover, evidence suggests that atrial fibrillation in obese patients shortens the refractory period of atrial and pulmonary vein myocardial cells.

Enhanced adiposity also induces alterations in electrocardiogram (ECG) parameters, including higher amplitude P waves with prolonged duration, extended PR intervals, and increased P wave terminal force. Animal studies indicate that diet-induced obesity may result in prolonged atrial conduction time and heterogeneous pulse conduction. Similar electrical changes have been observed in the context of atrial interstitial fibrosis, heightened inflammatory activity, and myocardial lipid accumulation. Interestingly, comparable changes have been documented in cases of congestive heart failure, hypertension, and myocardial infarction. However, the precise pathogenic role of complex signaling pathways (such as TGF, cTGF, and the endothelial system) in atrial fibrosis remains incompletely elucidated.

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